

A Compact, Low Loss Piezoelectric RF MEMS Relay with Sub 100-ns Switching Times

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Abstract – This work reports on the effort to develop a low voltage, high performance RF MEMS relay within an existing MEMS process. The $54 \times 43 \mu\text{m}^2$ relay achieved an insertion loss of under 0.2 dB from DC to 23.75 GHz at 5-V and an isolation from DC to 18-GHz of better than 30-dB. Additionally, the small, stiff structure achieved switching times of sub 100-ns with a 7-V actuation voltage and temperature measurements indicate stable operation from 0 °C to 125 °C. The relay was fabricated within an existing digital MEMS relay process, enabling integrated digital control for future RF systems.

Index Terms — Microswitches, microelectromechanical devices, piezoelectric devices, radiofrequency microelectromechanical systems, microwave devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

RF MEMS relays have been a very active area of research over the past two decades [1]. The devices are especially attractive to RF system designers for their wideband, low loss, high isolation and high linearity, all of which are achieved on the micron scale. Despite the advancements in semiconductor technologies over this same time span, RF MEMS relays still have the ability to provide higher performance system components in those areas [2]. Additionally, many of the devices consume very low amounts of power during steady-state operation, but can handle high levels of RF power across their contacts.

RF MEMS relay development has focused primary on two actuation mechanisms: electrostatic and piezoelectric [2]. Electrostatic devices are attractive since they are often directly integrable, via post-processing, with current CMOS fabrication flows. The devices, however, typically require high actuation voltages, 20 to 100-V. It is possible to reduce the voltage by reducing the gap or increasing the actuator area, but both of these alterations would increase the open-state capacitance and thus degrade higher frequency isolation [3].

An alternative MEMS technology utilizes a piezoelectric actuation mechanism to make and break electrical contact. These devices tend to be lower in voltage, typically sub 15-V, while still maintaining open-state gaps suitable for the high isolation state. Commonly used piezoelectric materials include aluminum nitride, zinc oxide and lead zirconate titanate (PZT). Of these, PZT provides the highest d_{31} piezoelectric coefficient, making it the optimal choice when designing a low voltage MEMS relay [4]. Traditionally, fabrication integration challenges with other semiconductor processes have limited PZT's usage. Recently, however, development began on a digital computation system composed entirely of PZT relays, which could alleviate this barrier in the future [5].

Fig. 1. Schematic of the RF MEMS relay.

Regardless of actuation mechanism, there is a desire to minimize the device area. Aside from a density advantage, Stefanini et al. showed that there were switching speed and isolation advantages to shrinking the dimensions [3]. Additionally, the smaller geometry minimized the impact of varying stress gradients in the fabrication process. In that work, a high yielding, $25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ relay with an off-state capacitance of 5-fF and an on-state resistance of 7- Ω at 55 V was demonstrated. By combining several devices, a composite structure achieved an on-state resistance of 1.4- Ω at the cost of increasing the off-state capacitance to 30-fF.

Unlike the electrostatic approach taken by Stefanini, this work considers device miniaturization via a PZT-based, piezoelectric actuation mechanism. The large deflection per volt provided by the PZT enable a design that minimizes contact area and maximizes the open state gap to provide suitable isolation, while also delivering sufficient force for a low insertion loss closed state. Presented here are the design and characterization of a PZT-based relay consisting of two 25- μm long, unimorph cantilevers with a single contact point system. The short actuators translate into a high resonance frequency, which minimizes switching times. Additionally, the device can be overdriven sufficiently to provide contact resistance stability over a wide range of temperatures.

Fig. 2. Optical Micrograph of the 25- μm long RF MEMS relay.

II. DEVICE DESIGN

The relay, shown schematically in Fig. 1, was designed to function as a low voltage, high performance RF switch while consuming a minimal area. The structure, which is similar to the device presented in [6], consists of two piezoelectric, unimorph actuators and a movable contact bar. The contact bar is mechanically coupled to the actuators' distal ends and situated below an overhanging gold (Au) cantilever. Unlike the device in [6], however, the RF signal line moves with the actuators in their vicinity. Additionally, this relay relies on a single contact point system formed via a ruthenium (Ru) dimple, placed below the overhanging cantilever, to create a Au-Ru contact pair. As contact force is inversely related to contact resistance and a byproduct of minimizing the device area is reduction in contact force, a single contact point design was necessary to minimize insertion loss [7].

When the device is at 0-V bias, an air gap separates the contact pad from the cantilever. At elevated voltages, the actuators deflect upward until the dimple presses against the overhanging cantilever, forming a low resistance connection between the RF input and output.

The actuators of the structure were optimized to enable sub 10-V operation while providing sufficient restoring force to prevent stiction. The unimorph actuator stack was composed of two sections: a lower elastic stack and upper piezoelectric

Fig. 3. Closed state S-parameter data for the 25- μm long RF MEMS relay at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

stack. The elastic stack was a silicon dioxide, silicon nitride, silicon dioxide thin film stack with thickness of 1073- $\text{\AA}$, 470- $\text{\AA}$ and 3520- $\text{\AA}$ respectively. Above that, a 5000- $\text{\AA}$ lead zirconate titanate thin film, produced with a Zr/Ti ratio of 52/48 and situated between two platinum films, was used as the piezoelectric material to enable closing the relay. Additional details on the fabrication process can be found in [5]. The final structure was inserted into a 50- Ω coplanar waveguide system with a 75- μm wide center conductor and 43- μm gap.

III. FABRICATED DEVICE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An optical micrograph of the fabricated device is shown in Fig. 2. The fabricated device consists of two, 25- μm long by 10- μm wide actuators and a 5- μm wide signal line in the vicinity of the actuators. The total device area was 58 x 43- μm^2 . All measurements performed on the devices were conducted in a lab-air environment with a SUSS PA-200 probe station. To evaluate the RF performance, a Keithley 2400 SourceMeter was used to provide the necessary bias voltages and an Agilent E8361A network analyzer measured the frequency response. Measurements were collected on-wafer, with 200- μm pitch GSG probes, over a frequency range from 0.1-GHz to 40.1-GHz at a power level of -17-dBm.

The S-parameter data, measured in both the closed state at a 5-V bias and the open state are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. The measurement system was calibrated to place the reference plane just prior to the CPW width transitions as shown in Fig. 2. The measurements show a sub 0.2-dB insertion loss from DC to 23.75-GHz in the closed state, indicating that the design achieves a sufficiently low contact resistance. The high isolation, better than 30-dB to 18-GHz, is attributed to a low open-state capacitance enabled via a 5 x 5 μm^2 contact area, coupled with a measured 480-nm open-state contact gap. Using Agilent's Advanced Design System software, the extracted closed-state resistance was 1.2- Ω and the open state capacitance 2.8-fF. This equates to a switch figure-of-merit of $f_c = R_{\text{On}}C_{\text{Off}} = 3.4$ fs.

Fig. 4. Open state S-parameter data for the 25- μm long RF MEMS relay at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 5. Measured S-Parameter data from 0°C to 125°C at the indicated actuation voltages for a 25- μm long RF MEMS relay.

TABLE I
SWITCHING TIME DATA MEASURED ON THE 25- μm RF MEMS RELAY

Actuation Voltage (V)	Average Switching Time (ns)	Minimum Switching Time (ns)	Maximum Switching Time (ns)	Std. Dev. (ns)
3	186	165.3	199.4	10.8
5	123.4	114.8	139.4	7.3
7	95.61	84.1	105	5.7
9	77.44	73.23	81	1.9

A potential issue for MEMS structures is temperature sensitivity. For this particular device, it was expected that the bias voltage necessary to achieve contact would increase as the temperature increases [6]. The reason for this was twofold; the switch should deflect away from the overhanging cantilever and the PZT would de-pole at a faster rate at elevated temperatures. The RF performance, however, was expected to be stable since the relay was capable of deflections much greater than the overhanging contact allowed, enabling it to overcome the aforementioned effects. To evaluate this, RF measurements were made from 0 to 125°C in 25°C increments. Measurements were taken three minutes after the system stabilized at each desired temperature. Bias voltage results exhibited the expected trend and ranged from a low of 2-V at 0°C to a high of 17-V at 125°C. Additionally, the RF performance, shown in Fig. 5, suffered minimal degradation at elevated temperatures.

A limitation of MEMS switches over their semiconductor counterparts has been switching time. It was anticipated that this RF MEMS relay's stiff actuators would improve upon the μs delays typically seen [2]. For the purpose of this work, switching time was defined as the transient delay between the 50% transition points of the actuation voltage and the output voltage. To evaluate this delay, a Keithley 2400 SourceMeter supplied a constant 3-V DC to the RF Input, an Agilent 33220A generated the square wave actuation bias to close the relay and a LeCroy WavePro 725Zi oscilloscope collected the response. The relay was measured at several actuation biases

and 10 cycles were collected at each bias. The results, reported in TABLE I, showed that the device was capable of operating at sub 100-ns speeds at the cost of higher voltage requirements.

IV. CONCLUSION

The RF MEMS relay presented here demonstrates a low-loss, low-voltage device with a compact size that enhances its isolation and switching speed. The device achieved an insertion loss of under 0.2 dB out to 23.75-GHz and an isolation better than 30-dB from DC to 18-GHz. Moreover, the device showed insertion loss stability from 0 °C to 125 °C. Additionally, the stiff actuators, aided by the reduced footprint of the device, enabled sub 100-ns switching speeds.

The restoring force of the device will be evaluated during future testing and, aided by the short, stiff actuators, is expected to be sufficient to prevent stiction-related failures. Additional efforts will also focus on evaluating power handling capabilities, lifetime and repeatability. In addition, the small size of the device lends itself to exploring parallel and series combinations for enhanced reliability.

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